

FIREFLY ALGORITHM OPTIMIZED PID CONTROLLER FOR AUTOMATIC GENERATION CONTROL OF AN INTERCONNECTED POWER SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This work presents, firefly algorithm based proportional integral derivative controller with for automatic generation control problem. Initially, a two area reheat thermal power system with Generation Rate Constraint (GRC) is considered and comparison was made between Proportional Integral (PI) and Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) is tested with considered system. From simulation results, it is observed that PID controller performs better compared to other controller. Robust analysis is made to show the capability of proposed controller by varying system parameters and loading conditions.

Keywords: Firefly Algorithm (FA); Proportional Integral Derivative controller (PID); robust analysis.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Now a day, Automatic Generation Control (AGC) plays an important role in power sector to maintain frequencies and tie-line powers of the interconnected power systems. Due to sudden increase load demand and other small disturbances in the system may deviate the frequencies and tie-line power from their nominal values. [1-3]. Therefore, there should be a mechanism to correct the frequencies and tie-line powers, However, scheduled values of frequencies and tie-line powers cannot be achieved by the primary control (speed governor system) alone. So, a secondary controller is necessary to abolish the effects of the load changes and small disturbances to keep the frequency at the standard value [4-7].

In last few decades, many researchers extensively studied the problem of AGC and they have proposed several secondary control strategies and optimization techniques. In past,